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The Great Difficulty of Making It to the End of the Month in the Italian Regions in the Period 2004-2021

It decreased by 40.78% on average in the Italian regions between 2004 and 2021

Istat calculates the great difficulty in making it to the end of the month. The variable is defined as the share of people in families who, when asked "Taking into account all available incomes, how does your family make it to the end of the month?" they choose the response mode "With great difficulty". The data refers to the period between 2004 and 2021 for the Italian regions.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the great difficulty in making ends meet in 2021. Campania is in first place by value of the great difficulty in making ends meet with a value of 31.9 units, followed by Abruzzo with an amount of 20.8 units, from Molise with a value of 16.8 units. In the middle of the table are Piedmont with a value of 6.8 units, followed by Calabria with a value of 6.4 units, and Marche with a value of 5.7 units. Trentino Alto Adige closes the ranking with a value of 2.9 units, followed by Tuscany with a value of 2.7 units and Umbria with a value of 2.3 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the percentage change in the great difficulty in making ends meet between 2004 and 2021. Abruzzo is in first place in terms of value of the percentage change in the great difficulty in making ends meet with a value of 45.45% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 14.3 units in 2004 up to 20.8 units in 2021. Molise follows with a percentage variation equal to an amount of 36.59% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 12.3 units up to a value of 16.8 units between 2004 and 2021. Campania follows with a variation equal to 21.76% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 26.2 units in 2004 up to a value of 31.9 units in 2021. In the middle of the table is Sardinia with a variation of -45.16% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 21.7 units in 2004 up to a value of 11.9 in 2021 corresponding to a variation of -9.8 unit. Marche follows with a variation equal to an amount of -46.23% corresponding to a reduction from an amount of 10.6 units in 2004 to a value of 5.7 units in 2021. Veneto with a variation equal to -55.56% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 9.9 in 2004 up to a value of 4.4 units in 2021.

Calabria closes the ranking with a variation of -76.30%, equal to a reduction from a value of 27 units in 2004 to a value of 6.4 units in 2021. Tuscany follows with a variation of -76.52% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 11.5 units in 2004 up to a value of 2.7 units in 2021. Umbria with a variation equal to -77.45% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 10.2 units in 2004 up to a value of 2.3 in 2021. Overall, the great difficulty in making it to the end of the month decreased on average by a variation equal to -40.78% between 2004 and 2021.

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The great difficulty in making ends meet in the Italian macro-regions between 2004 and 2021. The great difficulty in making ends meet has decreased in all Italian macro-regions. Among the macro regions that have significantly reduced the value of the great difficulty in making it to the end of the month there is Central Italy with an amount of -66.41%, followed by the Islands with -64.04%, the North-East with -56.32%, North with -35.48%, South with -33.87%, North-West with -22.45%, and South with -17.57%. Therefore, the value of the great difficulty in making ends meet has decreased in all Italian macro-regions. However, although the value of the great difficulty in making ends meet decreased between 2004 and 2021, there are still significant differences between macro-regions. The Italian macro-region that has the greatest impact on the great difficulty in making ends meet is Southern Italy. The value of the great difficulty in making ends meet in Southern Italy is equal to 5.18 times that of the North-East, equal to 4.58 times that of Central Italy, 3.28 times that of Northern Italy, 2.59 times that of the North-West, 2.05 times of the Islands, 1.20 times of the South.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we present a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Two clusters are identified:

- Cluster 1: Puglia, Campania, Sicily, Sardinia, Calabria, Basilicata, Abruzzo;
- Cluster 2: Emilia Romagna, Lombardy, Umbria, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Tuscany, Veneto, Marche, Piedmont, Trentino Alto Adige, Liguria, Valle d'Aosta, Lazio, Molise.

If we look at the average value of the clusters we can notice that the value of Cluster 1 is dominant compared to the value of Cluster 2, i.e. $C1 > C2$. We can see cluster 1 is essentially composed of southern regions. Molise is the only southern region that is part of cluster 2, i.e. the cluster that has a low value of great difficulty in making ends meet. There is therefore a clear contrast between the regions of Southern Italy, with medium-high levels of great difficulty in making ends meet, and the regions of Central-Northern Italy, with low levels of great difficulty in making ends meet.

Conclusions. The great difficulty in making it to the end of the month decreased on average in the Italian regions by 40.78% between 2004 and 2021. The only Italian regions in which the value of the great difficulty at the end of the month has increased are Abruzzo with +45.45%, Molise with +36.59%, and Campania with +21.76%. However, there is a significant inequality between the regions of Southern Italy and the regions of Northern Italy. In the regions of Southern Italy the value of the great difficulty in making ends meet is approximately 2.6 times higher than the regions of Northern Italy, and 3.28 times higher than the regions of Central Italy. It follows therefore that if on the one hand, the value of the great difficulty in making it to the end of the month has decreased in a general sense, on the other hand a significant regional gap between North and South persists.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange

for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

■ Piemonte ■ Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste ■ Liguria ■ Lombardia ■ Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol ■ Veneto
■ Friuli-Venezia Giulia ■ Emilia-Romagna ■ Toscana ■ Umbria ■ Marche ■ Lazio ■ Abruzzo ■ Molise ■ Campania ■ Puglia
■ Basilicata ■ Calabria ■ Sicilia ■ Sardegna

